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Effective Data Management: Implication for Educational Administration

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***Abstract:** This paper discussed the importance of effective data management for educational planning and administration in Nigeria. The paper is a review paper. The paper used secondary data to support every point raised. The paper employed systematic review system to collect data online and in the print resources. The paper concluded that effective data management in education will support educational planning, decision making, policy formulation and programme in education and resources allocation. Based on this, the paper recommends that government through ministries of education and agencies of education should ensure timely generation of current data that will aid educational management in Nigeria. Government should ensure officials in charge of data collection and management in the ministries and agencies are constantly trained on modern ways of data management.*

***Key words:** Effective Data Management, Educational Administration.*

Introduction

Education in Nigeria is generally stratified into three sectors, which are basic, post-basic/senior secondary, and tertiary education. However, another stratification based on the horizontal division of education into types is also available (National Planning Commission, 2009b). In this regard, early childhood care and development (or pre-primary education) is viewed as part of basic education but is specialized for younger children who are not yet of primary school age. Similarly, nomadic education is part of basic education but is for special groups of migrants. Adult and non-formal education may be part of basic education or may transcend it, as it can go as high as the post-basic level. Within basic, post-basic and even tertiary education, technical/vocational education is a subset. Teacher education is also a subset of tertiary education (NEEDS, 2014).

The responsibility for administering the education sector in Nigeria is shared among the federal, state and local governments. Thus, in the country's constitution, education is on the concurrent list, but the Federal Government is empowered to regulate all its sectors, engage in policy formation and ensure quality control. Also, the provisions of the constitution allow each tier of government to focus its responsibilities mainly on a sector of education. The Federal Government is involved directly in tertiary education. The states take care of secondary education, while the local governments handle primary education. Despite this arrangement, the Federal Government is expected to support the state and local governments in counterpart funding to enhance the quality of education in the country (NEEDS, 2014).

The administration of the education system is shared mainly among the education ministries at the federal and state levels, as well as statutory bodies referred to as commissions. There are commissions established for different sub-sectors of the education system and are charged with various responsibilities for the sub-sectors. The FME is responsible for the coherence of the national policy and procedures and for ensuring that the states' policies operate within the parameters of the national policy as adapted for local needs (Moja, 2000; NEEDS, 2014).

Educational administration is the arrangement of resources for the implementation of educational policies and programme. Educational administration needs data to aid planning and resources allocation. Ogunode (2021a) noted that one of the major function of education administration is planning of educational programme and projects. Planning is very vital to the realization of the objectives of secondary school education. Educational institutions must be planned to be able to achieve its objectives and education must be planned too to be able to realize its goals. Data is what is needed to plan and take decisions. Data is very important for planning educational programme. Without current educational data, planning is impossible. It is importance to discuss the importance of effective data management for educational administration.

Literature Review

Data

Borisade (2002) viewed data as a set of raw or unrefined values collected for the response variables for which each of the elements belongs to the sample. Ogundele (2017) defined data as information that are collected which may be stored, retrieved and utilized for effective educational planning. Data is the collection of values in the form of continuous or discrete that can give an event information. Data can be seen as factual information used for discussion. Data is the collection of row figures and values that can further give a piece of meaningful information. Nayon, (2017) viewed data as books, files, time table, admission register, attendance register, log book, syllabus, scheme of work, visitors' book,

punishment book, pupil's report card/ sheet, health record book, staff records, school cash book, record of school equipment/material, minutes book for meetings etc. Management on the other hand, is seen as getting things done through the effort of others.

According to Agbo (2006), data are language, mathematical or symbols, which are generally agreed upon to represent people, objects, events and concepts. Whereas information on the other hand, is the result of modelling, formatting, organizing or converting data in a way that increases the level of knowledge for its recipient. Osuala and Okeke (2006) viewed data as "a term that means fact of all kinds". Examples may include the one's date of birth, one's school grades, address, to mention but a few. Osaretin (2013) states that retrieved data are useful for the following: reference, decision making, planning budgeting purposes, evaluating the students' progress and determining the internal efficiency of the school.

Data Management

Data management is the systematic way of data organization, collection, interpretation and presentation for institutions' usage, and decision-making and improving institutions' effectiveness. Data management is the coordination of data within the institutions for supporting institutional' plans, decision making and operations. Data management involves the practical arrangement of data in systematic ways to improve organizational planning, resource allocation and decision-making. Data management is the practical way of handling data to support institutions' growth and development in terms of planning and decision-making. Data management is the application of organized and coordinated data for institutions' decision-making and planning for the realization of institutions' goals (Ogunode, Olowonefa & Idowu, 2024).

Effective Data Management

Effective data management is the systematical deployment of data that is achieving the purpose of deployment. Effective deals with attainment of set goals in an institutions.

Educational administration

Educational administration as concerned with integrating the appropriate human and material resources that are made available and made effective for achieving the purposes of a program of an educational institution (Nwiyi 2018). Educational administration is the process of identifying, mobilizing and utilizing scarce human and material resources relevant in education for the purpose of achieving specific educational goals efficiently and effectively (Osai and Kalagbor, 2017). Educational administration is the process whereby the school head as the chief executive of his staff controls them towards the achievement of the goals of the school system (Ezeocha, 1989). Educational administration as those activities a person performs when he is acting as a school principal or a superintendent (Walton 1991). Educational administration according to Okoroma, (2016) is the process that involves a careful and systematic use of methods, principles, plans and procedures necessary to achieve the educational objectives.

Ogunode (2020a) stated that educational administration is the application of educational resources to achieve educational goals. Educational administration is the act and process of using resources in an effective and efficiency ways to attain the various objectives of educational institutions. Educational administration deals with the planning and organizing human and materials resources to realize the goals of educational institutions. Educational administration is the systematic arrangement of educational input in an operational means to achieve the set goals of educational institution. Okoroma, (2016), outline the objectives of educational administration as follows: (1) to provide proper education

to students, (2) to ensure adequate utilization of all resources, (3) to ensure professional ethics and professional development among teachers, (4) to organize educational programmes for acquainting students with the art of democratic living and giving them excellent training in democratic citizenship, (5) to mobilize the community, (6) to organize co-curricular activities effectively for developing talents of students and work efficiency of educational teachers, (7) to get the work done, (8) to prepare students for taking their places in various vocations and avenues of life, (9) to train the students in developing scientific attitude and objective outlook among them towards all aspects and activities of life, and (10) to ensure qualitative improvement of education.

Method

This paper is a review paper and it explores the importance of effective data management in education. The study employed a documentary research method. The study relies on published secondary data from reputable sources including a review of published articles from reputable international journals such as CEON, Elsevier, Hindawi, JSTOR, IEEE, LearnTechlib SAGE, Nebraska and Springer amongst others. This research work used the Content Analysis and elimination method in the selection and analysis of papers, journals and abstracts used for the article. The design adopted for this article was to show an understanding of the data and importance of data in educational administration in schools in Nigeria. This study employed the content analysis method by selecting the relevant content of the various literature related to this study; and the literature review enabled the overall development of the study, which ordinarily centred on theoretical and conceptual exploration (Adapted from Ogunode & Ajap, 2021 in Ayeni, Ogunode, & Nonyelum, 2024).

Data Analysis on Impact of Effective Data Management on Educational Management

Educational Planning

Data is a planning tool. No effective planning can take place with availability of current data. Educational planning depend on data to succeed. Zafar, Mohammad & Yasir (2011) states that the availability of accurate, valid, reliable, and timely information is a pre-requisite for planning and management in any sector. Educational planning and management is no exception, it requires the availability and use of a diverse set of data for effective planning and successful management. To plan and manage in education sector, the following information should be available: demographic information, educational statistics, budget allocations for education sector and Human resource in education sector. Data helps education planners and decision-makers to know the structure and distribution of the population at a given time frame, as well as how it has changed in recent years. In other words, educational planning and management cannot be divorced from considerations about dynamics of population (i.e., its growth and change), as it deals with a 'target population' which is constantly changing in number, age and sex composition, and geographic distribution (Zafar, Mohammad & Yasir (2011). Durosaro (1997) and Ogunode (2021b) emphasizes the importance of efficient data management in aiding educational planning. They observed that quantitative data otherwise called statistics relate to figures needed for practical planning exercises are of great importance in the educational system. In the same vein, Nwankwo (1981) opined that quantitative data relates not only to the educational system but also to other systems related to education.

Decision making

The role of data in decision-making is very important and data make decisions to be accurate and relevant. Without data policy formulation and implementation will be useless. It is the life-line of any system as good education and sound economy are products of data based policy making. . Formulating

education Education data, like other social data, facilitates planning and constitute invaluable inputs for computing important social indicators which are used to monitor trends in the quality leading to improvement in policy decisions of the sector and better impact. It is the data based policy decision making in education that will ensure better returns on educational investment and stimulate economic growth and national development (Azuh, Joshua, & Ibietan, 2017). Nayon, (2017) discovered that effective data management in schools had influence on attainment of school goals, instructional leadership, evaluation of teachers, data management, decision-making based on data, professional development of teachers and co-ordination of school resources. Data based policy making ensures accountability in the management of education. Poor planning and non-use of data for policy decision-making is predominant in the educational sector and empirical information/ reports are rare (Azuh, et al 2017). Willms (1999) and Ogunode, Adah, Audu and Abubakar (2021) monitoring data can be used for policy formulation and also decision-makers in educational management can used data in many ways such as to identify specific problems, providing a basis for discussions towards a solution, assess effectiveness of interventions implemented at various levels, give rise to new ideas for influencing policy and practice and help administrators and teachers to reduce inequities.

Policy Formulation and Programme in Education

Data is needed for educational policy formulation and for designing of educational programme. Data provide information about what is needed to do in the programme. Data helps to identify the programme that given exact numbers of variable or people involved in the problem to be solved. Quartzafrika (2020) and Ogunode (2021) submitted that data are the first crucial step, then you need smart, objective analysis to make sense of the data and shape the narrative. Once the data supply side is up to date, the hope is that decision makers at all levels will increasingly demand relevant information to lay the foundation for policy making and budgeting. (Azuh, et al 2017) concluded that the success of any system of education is hinged on proper planning through the use of data. The need for data based policy making in national educational sector is more now than before particularly with the current revolution in information and communications technology which has made the world to become a global village. The inconsistencies observed in most educational sector decisions might make one infer that these decisions were based on incomplete information, intuition or rule of the thumb. Education data, like other social data, facilitates planning and constitute invaluable inputs for computing important social indicators which are used to monitor trends in the quality leading to improvement in policy decisions of the sector and better impact. Education data, like other social data, facilitates planning and constitute invaluable inputs for computing important social indicators which are used to monitor trends in the quality leading to improvement in policy decisions of the sector and better impact.

According to Durosaro (2002) school records are important tools ‘for effective planning and administration of schools, they do this through the following: 1) Assist pupils to know their progress and plan for their future (report sheet), 2) Assist parents and employers of labour with particular information about performance and general behavior of their children or prospective employees respectively. (Report sheet, punishment book), 3) Assist ex-pupils to get reference reports and recommendations for jobs or further studies (progress reports), 4) Assist a new school head to know what previously obtained in the school, thereby maintaining continuity in ‘the general educational process (log book, minutes book, inspection reports etc),

Resources allocation

Data management is vital to effective resource distribution in the system just like funds are vital to every organisation. Martin (2021) maintained that universities and colleges have a lot of resources at their disposal. To ensure resources like libraries, classrooms, laboratories, and the workforce are put into use, an effective database management system is necessary. The software keeps up-to-date information on all the available resources and helps the school management ensure proper allocation. An effective system can assist the school management in tracking resource distribution. This makes it easier to identify shortages of essential resources in the school and prevent unnecessary expenditure. A reliable Database management system (DBMS) analyses the school infrastructure development and provides information on school location, toilets, classrooms, library, labs, et cetera. With all this information, the school management can plan for resource allocation and improve productivity. Effective data administration in the education aids allocation of resources and it reduces resources wastages (Ogunode, Olowonefa & Idowu, 2024; Ogunode, & Usman, 2023).

Findings

The paper revealed that effective data management in education will support educational planning, decision making, policy formulation and programme in education and resources allocation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper explored the importance of effective data management for educational planning and administration in Nigeria. The paper concluded that effective data management in education will support educational planning, decision making, policy formulation and programme in education and resources allocation.

Based on this, the paper recommends that government through ministries of education and agencies of education should ensure timely generation of current data that will aid educational management in Nigeria. Government should ensure officials in charge of data collection and management in the ministries and agencies are constantly trained on modern ways of data management.

References

1. Azuh, D., Joshua, S. & Ibietan, J. (2017). The use of data in policy-making in Nigeria's educational sector: implications for national development, *Proceedings of INTED2016 Conference 7th-9th March 2016, Valencia, Spain*, 3683-3689
2. Ayeni, E, O., Ogunode, N., J. & Nonyelum, E., I (2024). Gender Mainstreaming and Tertiary Education in Nigeria: A Proposal to Replace Structural Violence with Peacebuilding. *American Journal of Education and Evaluation Studies*, 1(2),31-40.
3. Borisade, F. T. (2002). *Introductory statistics and vocamentric*. Integrity Publishers, Ibadan
4. Fasasi, Y.A., (2004). School record keeping: A strategy for management of nigerian secondary education institutions. *Ilorin Journal of Education*, 23, 73-78.
5. Martin, H. (2021). What are the benefits of data management in the education sector? <https://www.talentedladiesclub.com/articles/what-are-the-benefits-of-data-management-in-the-education-sector/>
6. Moja, T. (2000). *Nigeria Education Sector Analysis: An Analytical Synthesis of Performance and Main Issues*. Report produced for the World Bank.

7. Nayan, J. (2017). Data management for effective administration Of secondary schools in Delta State. A Dissertation submitted to post graduate school in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of master degree (M.ED) in educational administration of the delta state university Abraka.
8. NOUN (undated). Implementation of Educational Policy. Lagos, Nigeria
9. NEEDS, (2014). *Needs assessment in the Nigerian education sector*. International organization for migration, Abuja, Nigeria.
10. Ogunode, N,J (2021a) Challenges Preventing Effective Planning of Education in Nigeria and the Ways Forward,*Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, Vol (2) 2, pp- 30-39
11. Ogunode N, J. (2021). Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Nigeria: Problems and Suggestions. *Central Asian Journal of social sciences and history*: 02 (02).p:90-102
12. Ogunode N., J, Adah S, Audu E, I, & Abubakar M. (2021). An Investigation into the Challenges Facing Collection and Distribution of Educational Data in F.C.T Educational Institutions, Abuja, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business, Technology, and Organizational Behavior (IJBTOB)* ISSN: 2775-4936 Vol. 01 (02),105-113
13. Ogunode N., J. (2021b).Data Collection and Distribution in Nigerian Higher Institutions: Problems and Way Forward. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, (9), 704-714
14. Ogunode, N., J. & Usman, Z (2023). Deployment of Educational Management Information System (EMIS) in Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Nigeria. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* (12),1-13
15. Ogunode, N., J., Olowonefa J., A & Idowu, O., M (2024). Effective Data Management and University Education Administration in Nigeria. *Synergy: Cross-Disciplinary Journal Of Digital Investigation*,2(4),32-39
16. Ogunode N. J., & Ajape, T. S. (2021). Office of the Registrar in Nigerian Public Universities: Problems and Suggestions. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, (12), 25-32
17. Ogundele, M.O (2019) Ethical issues in research data management. Way forward. In C.sibling (Ed) *Data Management in Research*. Germany: Igi press.
18. Okoroma, N. S. (2016). *Perspectives of educational management, planning & policy analysis*. Port Harcourt: Minson publishers.
19. Okoroma, N. S. (2016). Oil pipeline vandalization in the Niger Delta: Implications for funding education in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Oil and Gas Technology*, 1(1), 8-18.
20. QuartzAfrica (2020). Poor data hurts African countries' ability to make good policy decisions. <https://qz.com/africa/762729/poor-data-is-hurting-african-countries-ability-to-make-good-policy-decisions/>
21. Wallin, J. (1999). *Towards Performance Evaluation in Indonesian Education: Rewarding Effective Performance through the Civil Service Functional Credit System*. Jakarta: PT. Hickling Indonesia.
22. Zafar I. M., Mohammad, N. A. & Yasir. I. (2011). National Education Management Information System Academy of Educational Planning and Management Ministry of Professional & Technical Training, Islamabad